

Real-Time Analytics of Multimodal Physiological Measures Based on Cognitive Assessment

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Abstract

Cognitive models are computational programs that simulate human performance, using integrated metrics, an example of which are physiological metrics that measure user emotional response. They are most useful in Human-computer Interaction (HCI) for predicting task times and performance; the result is mostly assisting users and also acting as immediate surrogate users. Models would also be easier to operate and apply if cognitive models interact with the same interfaces that the users interact with. This paper develops a cognitive assessment model by encapsulating operating procedures as an interface management system, with an integrated multimodal physiological measure sensor (Skin conductance response, Skin temperature, and Pupil dilation), this is analogous and similar to a user interface management system (UIMS). We present an experimental setup where the model is used to analyse user physiological response to visual activities and demonstrates its correlates to user cognitive response on the cognitive assessment system by basic annotation of response point to task performance. The system has a multi-accessibility function for user and evaluator access. This will help to exploit the synergy in the discipline of cognitive assessment modeling and HCI.

Keywords: Cognitive assessment modeling, Human-computer interaction, Multimodal physiological measure, User interface, User interface management system, Encapsulating operation

Measure Based Cognitive Assessment

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1 INTRODUCTION

In this section, we discuss briefly the synergy between cognitive assessment modeling human physiological and human-computer interaction by relating cognitive models as a simulation of human behaviour and physiological correlates. The task performed could range from complexity to simple mental arithmetic to real-time computer controlling simulations based on

systems controls [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. These systems could become more powerful and useful in the future. We derived a cognitive analytic that integrates physiological measures in a multimodal feature that allows cognitive access as a direct means to interface with users and also to evaluators. This is adopted based on ideas from the user interface management system (UIMSs). It recognises cognitive models to be utilised as interface design and also an evaluation tool on a

far broader scene for interactive systems as seen in previous models [6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. The multimodal aspect includes integration for one of more physiological measure sensors (Figure 1) such as SCR, ST, and Pupil changes integrated into a single board circuit frame.

1.1 Skin Conductance Response SCR

The SCR is the measure of electrical changes in the skin, as a result of sweat [11, 12, 13, 14, 15] when the user is involved in a different activity such as a complex task like finding a solution to a mathematical problem. This activates the cells of the skin to become more sensitive and responsive to visual stimuli. The paper adopts fingerprint detection by motion tracking of moisture content on the skin, usually, the first two middle fingers are placed on a touch screen surface or a camera lens of a mobile phone. This measures and simulations the electrical changes of the skin surface. The touchpad connects to the lens port of the screen and captures the fingerprint-like the mechanism in mouse pad. Response in motion and magnitude is saved as the sensor modules change with time. The physiological measure is used in synchronous with other metrics and user interaction.

1.2 Skin Temperature

The skin temperature [16, 17, 18, 19, 20] records how hot or cold a person feels during this interaction, this parameter is obtained for the degree of hotness of the moisture content of the skin as measured from the touchpad. The clinical temperature is probably the most accurate metric for the measure of skin temperature but the ST used here is strictly based on simulation and accuracy is close to 100% as compared to the natural or clinical temperature measurement. This physiological metric is used harmoniously with other measures and used as an incentive for the other physiological measures. More than one metric is the best fit for a user interaction assessment on cognitive response or the affected state of the user.

1.3 Pupil dilation

The pupil response is the change in pupil size [21, 22, 23, 24, 25], and can interpret the cognitive workload of the user in novel ways as described in current research [24]. The pupil changes, not only tell of changes in light intensity but also the cognitive load of the user. In some research, it is viewed that pupil dilation in response to light intensity or a drowsy state of a person, and pupil constriction is simply implies concentrated intensity to attention and also focus. This physiological measure is a strong incentive for other physiological responses. The pupil's response can be tracked by simply facing a web camera on a PC for a locally inclined study, in this case, instead of an eye tracker since employing an eye tracker is usually expensive in some cases, the webcam is

an adopted way of utilising camera lens to measure and track eye movements on visual screen.

2 METHOD

The method adopted here follows an experimental setup where a few participants (10 people) were selected to sit in front of a PC with a webcam (Figure 2) for the initial study on model testing. Their physiological measure is recorded while they interact with visual stimuli (a mathematical problem). They were simply asked to find the shortest solution to a differential equation. Their cognitive level is tested to determine if they find this problem, stressful, relaxed, or average response while dealing with the problem. The eye positions were calibrated on the PC to track and measure their eye movement through pupil tracking in real time. Their first two middle fingers were placed on a touchpad with electrodes to record their SCR and ST through moisture detection.

2.1 Moisture content

In other to measure the moisture content in the skin, the keratinous layer is first detected from a fingerprint, and magnetic flux from the touchpad measures the moisture content in continuous kHz/secs, for electrodes, it is measured as mium per second (μ s). The moisture content on the skin is given as:

$$MC_{skin} = \frac{w_{skin-Con} - w_{Environment}}{w_{Environment}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where

1. $MC_{skin-Con}$ = moisture content expressed as a percentage due to reaction on the skin.
2. $w_{skin-Con}$ = weight in skin condition to task performance.
3. $w_{Environment}$ = weight of skin to environmental constraint.

The predicted fingerprint, in this case, is equivalent to the moisture content of the skin due to task performance and as a result of the electrical changes of the skin due to reaction to perceived stimuli, this is given as:

$$X_i = MC_{skin}(t)n \quad (2)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^3x}{dy^3} &= a \frac{d^2x}{dy^2} + b \frac{dx}{dy} + c; \\ x &= \int_{i=1}^n 3 \frac{d^2x}{dy^2} - 2a \frac{dx}{dy} - bx; \\ y &= ax + c \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where a, b, c are constants due to environmental constraints, x represents the rate of change of conduction

Figure 1: The schematic diagram of a Multimodal physiological measuring sensor.

Figure 2: User interacting with visual content with fingers placed on a wireless touchpad.

with the touchpad through the moisture content MC_{skin} as an input matrix of the sensor output produced by the image detector, and this produces the resultant reaction y as a vector matrix, a cognitive response or reaction to stimuli on the skin surface. The skin temperature (ST) with time t is measured as:

$$\frac{d^3(ST)}{dt^3} = a \frac{d^2(ST)}{dt^2} + b \frac{d(ST)}{dt} + c; \quad (4)$$

For a custom EDA and ST response of this form, the noise is very intense, a Savitsky Golay filter (Equation 5) is used to remove noise and anomalies for a smooth representation of the response variable y . The behaviour of the filter is influenced by selecting appropriate filter

coefficients. The moving average filter is a polynomial fit that smoothens the derivative by adjusting the coefficients of the equation. The data points np defines the data used for the smoothing.

$$y_i = \frac{1}{h} \left\{ \sum_{i=-\frac{np-1}{2}}^{\frac{np-1}{2}} a_i x_{t+i} \right\} \quad (5)$$

2.2 Pupil Response

The pupil response measure is modelled as a physiological time-invariant non-linear delay differential first-order equation that defines the changes in pupil area and diameter as a function of the lighting in the surrounding environment which is given as:

$$\frac{dm}{dD} \times \frac{dD}{dt} + 2.30 \tanh^{-1} \left(\frac{D-4.9}{3} \right) = 5.2 - 0.45 \ln \left(\frac{\varphi[t-\tau]}{4.8 \times 10^{-10}} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where D is the constant change in diameter as measured in millimetres and $\varphi[t-\tau]$ is the luminosity in an intense light that reaches the retina of the eye time t , which can be defined as $\varphi = IA$: the luminance reaching the eye in *lumens/mm²*. τ is the pupil latency, a delay that lies between the point in time where the light pulse touches the retina and beginning or rise in the iridal reaction due to nerve transmission, movement and activation in delay. dm , dD and dt are the derivatives of m function, the pupil diameter at time t based on research, the pupil constriction in velocity is approximately three times faster than the re-contraction speed. The simulation is obtained using the following step size for the numerical solver, given as:

$$\begin{aligned} dt_c &= \frac{T_c - T_p}{3s} \\ dt_d &= \frac{T_c - T_p}{3s} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Here, dt_c and dt_d are the derivative dt for both dilation and constriction, which are measured in milliseconds T_c and T_p are the current and previous simulation times in milliseconds. s is a constant parameter that affects the dilation and constricting velocity of the eye movement, this is different for every individual. The section below describes the results derived from the adopted model specification and simulation of these concepts.

3 RESULT

The section on the right of the window interface (Figure 3) captured the fingerprint from the touchpad, synchronous events from the physiological response are combined and a response peak for optimal response is detected at tonic and phasic changes, this classified the phasic response as stress, relaxed, complex and average cognitive response of the user to a mathematical problem. The baseline of the response is considered very significant because it defines the phasic changes and delimits

the tonic phases. The latency point is inconsistent since all skin textures are different and response spikes are difficult to detect in dehydrated skin, such a case usually shows low-level peaks and a lack of significant spikes in Electrodermal activity. The electrodermal changes of the cognitive assessment are a combination of the SCR, ST, and Pupil responses (reaction of the pupil as measured from the webcam). The system has options to select view tonic and phasic changes and their corresponding cognitive level and state at a particular point in time. The system is most applicable in mobile phones or current Windows desktops and it is now operated as a standalone for automatic camera integration on startup.

Figure 3: Window interface of the cognitive assessment model with integrated physiological response and fingerprint capture.

The cognitive state of the user is used to annotate the physiological response to phasic changes using a peak detection algorithm that predicts phasic response points. The prediction accuracy is tested and Figure 4 and 5 shows the aggregate error bar for the five cognitive responses of the users to the mathematical problem task. From the EDA, the 'stress' response has the least error in detection from all response phases. This margin also delineates a higher response state in the middle state

of response or phasic detection. Stress in mathematical problems is usually the most significant response from a person when based on a subjective view from a general perspective and this correlates to the cognitive model's results.

Usually, the outer response state as measured from the magnetic flux in the touch sensor of the host system is the same as the inner response state of the receptor. In this case, the 'stress' cognitive state is detected with less error at the inner lens level than for the recorded EDA. The error bars are the graphical representation of the difference in variability of the response tracking for all physiological responses in synch, it indicates the error or uncertainty in the response measure. Error for both cognitive responses detected in both EDA and lens or magnetic flux is greater than the confidence level at 98%. These quartiles are not similar in terms of the measure of EDA with electrodes.

4 CONCLUSION

The paper investigates the cognitive assessment of users through real-time analytics of multimodal physiological measuring sensors. The procedure follows the development of a cognitive assessment model by encapsulating operating procedures as an interface management system, with an integrated multimodal physiological measure sensor (Skin conductance response, Skin temperature, and Pupil dilation), this process is analogous to a user interface management system (UIMS). We presented an experimental setup where the model uses analytical user physiological response to visual activities and represents its correlates to user cognitive response on the cognitive assessment system by basic annotation of response points to task performance. The system has a multi-accessibility function for user and evaluator access. This leads to exploiting the synergy in the discipline of cognitive assessment modeling through integrated physiological response measure human-computer interaction. The next stage of the project will be testing the predictability on the filters applied to the physiological response with some standard and existing methods of response detection in physiological measures.

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References

- [1] Douglas C Engelbart. Augmenting human intellect: A conceptual framework. In *Augmented Education in the Global Age*, pages 13–29. Routledge, 2023.
- [2] Douglas C Engelbart. Augmenting human intellect: a conceptual framework (1962). 2021.
- [3] Gardner Campbell. Education, information technologies, and the augmentation of human intellect. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 38(5): 26–31, 2006.
- [4] Douglas C Engelbart and William K English. A research center for augmenting human intellect. In *Proceedings of the December 9-11, 1968, fall joint computer conference, part I*, pages 395–410, 1968.
- [5] Douglas C Engelbart. Augmenting human intellect: a conceptual framework (1962). 2021.
- [6] Douglas C Engelbart. *Augmenting human intellect: Experiments, concepts, and possibilities*. Stanford Research Institute Menlo Park, 1965.
- [7] Cassandra Xia and Pattie Maes. The design of artifacts for augmenting intellect. In *Proceedings of the 4th Augmented Human International Conference*, pages 154–161, 2013.
- [8] Gardner Campbell. Education, information technologies, and the augmentation of human intellect. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 38(5): 26–31, 2006.
- [9] DC Engelbart. Human intellect augmentation techniques final report. Technical report, NASA, 1969.
- [10] Douglas Engelbart. The augmented knowledge workshop. In *A history of personal workstations*, pages 185–248. 1988.
- [11] Douglas C Engelbart. Advanced intellect-augmentation techniques. 1972.
- [12] Mark H Ashcraft. Cognitive psychology and simple arithmetic: A review and summary of new directions. *Mathematical cognition*, 1(1):3–34, 1995.
- [13] Stig Arlinger, Thomas Lunner, Björn Lyxell, and M Kathleen Pichora-Fuller. The emergence of cognitive hearing science. *Scandinavian journal of psychology*, 50(5):371–384, 2009.
- [14] George Siemens, Fernando Marmolejo-Ramos, Florence Gabriel, Kelsey Medeiros, Rebecca Marrone, Srecko Joksimovic, and Maarten de Laat. Human and artificial cognition. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 3:100107, 2022.
- [15] Niall M Broomfield, Ken Laidlaw, Emma Hickabottom, Marion F Murray, Rachel Pendrey, Janice E Whittick, and David C Gillespie. Post-stroke depression: The case for augmented, individually tailored cognitive behavioural therapy. *Clinical Psychology & Psychotherapy*, 18(3):202–217, 2011.

Figure 4: Error bar for the cognitive response of users to a mathematical problem.

Figure 5: Error bar for the cognitive response of users to the second mathematical problem.

- [16] Mary Hegarty. The cognitive science of visual-spatial displays: Implications for design. *Topics in cognitive science*, 3(3):446–474, 2011.
- [17] Xiaoping Hu and David G Norris. Advances in

high-field magnetic resonance imaging. *Annu. Rev. Biomed. Eng.*, 6:157–184, 2004.

- [18] Pottumarthi V Prasad. *Magnetic resonance imaging: methods and biologic applications*, volume 124. Springer Science & Business Media, 2008.
- [19] Tianzi Jiang, Yong Liu, Feng Shi, Ni Shu, Bing Liu, Jiefeng Jiang, and Yuan Zhou. Multimodal magnetic resonance imaging for brain disorders: advances and perspectives. *Brain Imaging and Behavior*, 2:249–257, 2008.
- [20] Ruijie Huang, Xingyu Zhou, Guiyuan Chen, Lan-hong Su, Zhaoji Liu, Peijie Zhou, Jianping Weng, and Yuanzeng Min. Advances of functional nanomaterials for magnetic resonance imaging and biomedical engineering applications. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Nanomedicine and Nanobiotechnology*, 14(4):e1800, 2022.
- [21] Robert W Brown, Y-C Norman Cheng, E Mark Haacke, Michael R Thompson, and Ramesh Venkatesan. *Magnetic resonance imaging: physical principles and sequence design*. John Wiley & Sons, 2014.
- [22] Yaping Lin, Ke Zhang, Ruihong Zhang, Zhending She, Rongwei Tan, Yubo Fan, and Xiaoming Li. Magnetic nanoparticles applied in targeted therapy and magnetic resonance imaging: crucial preparation parameters, indispensable pre-treatments, updated research advancements and future perspectives. *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, 8(28): 5973–5991, 2020.
- [23] ACKNON LED GEMENTS. Advanced research projects agency, department of defence.
- [24] James Pippine, Douglas Hackett, and Adam Watson. An overview of the defense advanced research projects agency’s learning locomotion program. *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, 30(2): 141–144, 2011.
- [25] Nancy C Groves, Thomas T Huang, Ming S Chang, et al. Geometric characteristics of darpa (defense advanced research projects agency) suboff models (dtrc model numbers 5470 and 5471). *David Taylor Research Center Bethesda MD Ship Hydromechanics Dept*, 1989.